
COMPARATIVE EFFECTS OF BLENDED LEARNING AND LECTURE INSTRUCTIONAL STRATEGIES ON ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE OF UPPER BASIC SOCIAL STUDIES STUDENTS IN DELTA STATE

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ABSTRACT

This study compared the effects of blended learning and lecture instructional strategies on the academic performance of Upper Basic Social Studies students. Two research questions and two hypotheses were stated and tested using relevant data collected. A quasi-experimental equivalent design, specifically a 2x2 factorial design, was adopted for the study. The subjects comprised all Upper Basic II Social Studies students from three purposively selected secondary schools in Delta State. The selected schools were randomly assigned to the groups: blended learning strategy and lecture method. Each group consisted of 62 students (blended learning instructional strategy) and 65 students (lecture method), making a total of 127 sampled students. Treatments were administered to the groups for six weeks. A Social Studies Performance Test (SSPT), with a reliability coefficient of 0.77, was used to measure students' performance before and after the treatments. The students' pre-test and post-test scores were analyzed using mean, standard deviation analysis of variance (ANOVA) and independent t-test. The findings showed that there was a significant difference in the academic performance of Social Studies students taught with blended learning compared to those taught with the lecture method. Results also indicated a statistically significant difference in the mean academic performance scores of urban and rural Social Studies students taught using blended learning instructional strategies in Delta State. Based on these findings, it was concluded that students taught using blended learning strategies performed significantly better than those taught with the lecture instructional strategy. Consequently, it was recommended, among others, that Social Studies teachers at the Upper Basic level should adopt blended learning strategies in their instructional delivery, as the method has been proven to significantly enhance students' academic performance compared to the traditional lecture method

Keywords: Academic Performance, Social Studies Blended Learning, Lecture Method. Urban and Rural Students

INTRODUCTION

Social Studies as a school subject emerged to improve the citizenry. The major objective of Social Studies is to ensure acquisition of relevant knowledge and rational thinking ability which is a prerequisite to personal growth and development for the betterment of oneself and that of the society. Achieving these objectives lies in the quality of instruction given in the classroom. Social Studies being a unique subject requires variety of instructional strategy to be able to make impact on the lives of the learners. In light of this, the teaching of Social Studies using different instructional strategy which are learner-centered becomes indispensable. Hence this is a major reason why process oriented guided learning and blended learning as one of the student centered strategies which help in making the teaching and learning of Social Studies active and meaningful cannot be underemphasize. Social Studies has its major focus in the promotion of civic competence, integration of knowledge skills and attitudes in resolving societal problems, issues and challenges. It is a discipline that ruminates and explores the dynamism of society and the changing nature of knowledge. In spite of the important place of Social Studies in our educational system, including its role in relation to societal values, problems, changing circumstances and democratic heritage, some student performance are still unsatisfactory in Delta State (Ogheneakoke, Obro & Benike, 2018)

Students' unsatisfactory performance has prompted researchers to delve into the underlying causes and explore strategies to enhance classroom instruction and students' academic performance. Obro, Ogheneakoke and Akpochafo (2021), asserted that an appropriate instructional strategy should encompass the effective instructional strategy of teaching a subject. Teaching effectiveness is contingent upon utilising a process that elicits a desirable attention in the learner's behaviour. The teaching objective should encompass cultivating students' interest in the subject matter and enhancing their academic performance. Employing innovative and outcome-driven approaches is imperative and vital to attain this crucial objective. Over the years, many instructional strategies have been recognized and tried out by teachers. These instructional strategies include demonstration, laboratory work, simulation, concept mapping, constructivist learning, problem based, inquiry instructional strategy, small group teaching and peer tutoring, are all perceived good and effective instructional strategy that can be used for instructional strategy (Oyovwi, 2015). While the teacher factor is important, equally important in the teaching and learning situation is the method and the right pedagogical method.

Instructional strategy is very vital in any teaching-learning situation. The teaching instructional strategy adopted by the teacher may either promote or hinder students learning. It may sharpen mental activities, which are the basis of social power, or it may discourage initiatives and curiosities, thus making self-reliance and survival difficult. Ekuigbo (2025) stated that teachers need to be well equipped in methodology as the teacher is responsible for translating policies into action in the classroom even the best curriculum are the most perfect syllabus remain dead unless quickened into life by the right method of teaching by the teacher whose responsibility of the teachers to help students attain maximum achievement in their learning tasks. Such a responsibility includes the use of appropriate instructional strategy in teaching (Sukolatambaya, 2018).

The lecture instructional strategy is a type of instructional strategy in which the instructor speaks to the class verbally on a particular topic, theme, or idea. Teachers use minimal or no instructional strategies to give preplanned lessons to the students (Ibitomi, Adefila & Aina, 2018). The lecture instructional strategy adopted in the teaching of social

science subjects has been designated as a teacher-centred approach. A teacher-centred approach is an instructional strategy where a teacher presents information to students, who are expected to passively receive the knowledge being presented. This instructional strategy makes the teachers feel in charge in the classroom setting. The lecture instructional strategy is also a set of actions or activities organised by the teacher and delivered to the student in an instructional manner to enable him to acquire and process knowledge, retain and recall it, and apply it to new life tasks and issues. The lecture instructional strategy is one of the most popular and fastest modes of disseminating knowledge, and it is frequently used in traditional classroom instruction. Learners who do not know how to be active participants in lectures have relied on dictation, copying directly from textbooks or chalkboards, memory, and repetition for learning (Musengimana, Kampire & Ntawiha, 2021).

Researchers such as Wanjohi (2016); Sanda and Mazila (2017) advocated the use of lectures, but stressed that the issue stems from how they are delivered, not from their fundamental incapacity to produce meaningful learning. In practise, most teachers using lecture instructional strategy normally fail to engage students or drive them to take ownership of their learning due to the need to cover the syllabus before the end of term (Andala & Ng'umbi, 2016). When students who have learnt through process oriented guided inquiry and blended learning instructional strategies are assessed in class, they appear to be more adept at applying what they have learned in immediate problem-solving situations. The technique has also been found to encourage "rote" learning, which might result in the correct response without the capacity to explain why a certain concept was employed. Angelin and Cecily (2015) stated that using a lecture instructional strategy to convey knowledge to the learners should be avoided since it only provides weak education and learning capabilities. It is therefore very pertinent to search for an approach to the teaching of Social Studies that aims at understanding rather than juggling facts (Afrasiabifar & Asadolah, 2019).

One of such approaches is blended learning. Blended learning is a teaching strategy that combines traditional instructor-led classroom activities with technology and digital media. Blended learning combines face-to-face, instructor-led learning with online or digital course components, giving students more autonomy over their learning path and pace. In blended learning, the in-person and online elements work together to create a richer learning experience and do not simply duplicate course content in varying formats. The blended instructional strategy involves the effective combination of different modes of lesson delivery, models of teaching and styles of learning which are exercised in an interactively meaningful learning environment. Blended instructional strategy is a combination of multimedia application and classroom face-face teaching and learning activities, it is also the use digital resources in an optimal way in order to improve student learning outcomes (Etaneki, 2023). Blended learning combines the best features of classroom interaction and multimedia based teaching instructional strategy. Blended instructional strategy in this study refers to a teaching instructional strategy involving both face-to-face/live instruction and multimedia/digital based instruction. It involves the effective combination of digital resources and traditional instructional strategy of lesson delivery.

Another factor that may influence or moderate students' performance irrespective of instructional strategies used in the classroom is school location. School location, students attend schools at different geographical locations which is the place a school is situated. The location of a school could be urban or rural area. According to Oriaku (2017) urban area comprised of the processes by which life in metropolitan areas is organized and operated. These processes may be grouped into four major categories of; infrastructure, built environment/planning, administration and human services, it includes multiple local

governments, economies, and demographics. Cabral (2018) defined urban area as the centre of economic and social development characterized by the mixture of residential, commercial, agricultural and industrial activities. Urban life style, and by extension, urban area can be defined by three population characteristics which are on the basis of three (3) variables namely, number, density of settlement and degree of heterogeneity of the urban population. Urban areas are those thickly populated towns or cities with the basic amenities and facilities that make life comfortable like human structures such as houses, commercial buildings, roads, bridges, and railways, hospitals, local government headquarters etc. An urban area includes the city itself, as well as the surrounding areas, while rural areas are those places distinguished from towns and cities with little or no basic amenities or facilities and no government headquarters (Funk & Wagnalls, 2018). Okorie and Eze (2016) reported that the performance of urban students is quite higher than students in the rural areas, however urban students achieved higher and better than their rural counterparts. In the researcher's view, the urban students may have performed better than the rural students as a result of teachers not wanting to go to rural schools to teach, students spend so much time on farm work at the expense of the time they should spend on their study. From the foregoing, it is likely that differences in location is factor capable of influencing and causing variation in the effect of a particular instructional strategy used by a teacher on academic performance in Social Studies. This study therefore investigated the effect of blended instructional strategies on students' academic performance of upper basic Social Studies students in Delta State and ascertained if the effect is location dependent.

Statement of the Problem

In recent times the teaching and learning of Social Studies have been faced with numerous problems that are capable of impeding the realization of its objectives and one of such problems is unsatisfactory academic performance. The problem addressed in this study stems from the need to diversify the teaching instructional strategy used in the field of learning and education, particularly, where the results of Social Studies performance tests indicate a low level of performance of Social Studies students. This is reflected in students' performance of low-level learning ability and academic performance of Social Studies students. This has led teachers to introduce various teaching instructional strategy to improve students' learning. Over the years there had been a decline in final or placement exam of Social Studies student. This could be as a result of the teacher's use of ineffective instructional strategies in Social Studies teaching which among other factors have contributed to the student's poor academic performance at the upper secondary school.

Social Studies as a subject has grown beyond traditional way of learning, hence there is a need for teachers to seek for some learning strategies that will enable students develop faster learning ability, that involve critical thinking, impact in their lives as well as to enhance students' academic performance. The available literature on instructional strategy of teaching in Social Studies Education suggests the need to employ new and innovative teaching strategy such as blended learning. Therefore, the problem of this study is posed as a question; "What is the effect of blended learning on academic performance of Social Studies students in Delta State?"

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study

1. What is the difference in the academic performance of Social Studies students taught with blended learning and lecture method in Delta State?

2. What is the effect of school location on Social Studies students taught using blended learning and lecture instructional strategy in Delta State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significant.

1. There is no significant effect of blended learning on academic performance of Social Studies student in Delta State?
2. There is no significant effect of school location on Social Studies students taught using blended learning and lecture instructional strategy in Delta State?

Methodology

A quasi-experimental, non-equivalent pre-test, post-test, control group design was adopted for the study. The population of this study comprised a total 77, 296 Upper Basic 8 Social Studies students drawn from 485 public secondary school in Delta State from the 2024/2025 session. A sample of 127 upper basic 8 students drawn from two secondary schools out of the four hundred and sixty-seven (467) public secondary schools in three Senatorial District of Delta State. This is because the study is a quasi-experimental study. The multistage sampling technique at four levels using the balloting techniques was used to select the sample for the study. The first stage of sampling was the senatorial district, which was used as the sampling units. In the second stage of sampling, each of the senatorial district, one local government area was randomly selected. In the third stage of sampling, two schools were selected from each of the local government area using the purposive sampling techniques as a third stage of sampling. Also the purposive technique was used in selecting all the students from the two school, from each of the school, an arm of Upper basic two was sampled at the fourth stage of sampling.

All the students in that arm from the two secondary schools constituted the subjects for the experimental study. In selecting the schools for the study, only mixed schools were considered suitable for the study as male and female was one of the variables investigated. In other words, all single schools were eliminated from the study. The ballot instructional strategy was used to assign these schools to the experimental and control groups.

The instrument that was used for the study is Social Studies Performance Test (SSPT) developed by the researcher. The SSPT was used for data collection. The SSPT consists of two sections. Section A contained instruction on student's bio-data (group number and location). Section B consists of 50 multiple-choice items with option letter A-D covering four concepts or topics. The multiple choice items were scored dichotomously (correct or wrong).

The face validity of the Social Studies Performance Test (SSPT) was done by one experience Social Studies teacher and one expert in measurement and evaluation. The content validity was carried out on the Social Studies Performance Test using table of specification. The researcher carried out a pre-trial test of the SSPT on fifty (50) students of upper basic Secondary school outside the intended area of study. Data collected through the test was used to compute the reliability of the instrument. The Kuder-Richardson formula -21 was used to compute the reliability index and co-efficient value of 0.77 was obtained. This value was considered high, thus the instrument was adjudged consistent and reliable. The instructional strategy was also considered appropriate since the test-items were dichotomous. The sampled schools were assigned to each of the treatment groups, On the first day of the experiment,

pretests were administered on the two groups using the Social Studies Performance test (SSPT). The pretest determined the equivalency of the groups and to measure level of prior knowledge of the students and the topics on which the test was based. The actual instruction was carried out by the regular Social Studies teacher in each of the sample schools using the lesson plan developed by the researcher for each group for six weeks. In the control group, the teacher only used the lecture instructional strategy of teaching. The experiment (instructional activities) lasted for six weeks. At the end of the instruction a summative posttest was administered on the students with the same instrument used during the pretest. The research questions were answered using mean scores and standard deviations of scores. Hypotheses were tested with t-test analysis to determine the difference that exists between the variables at 0.05alpha levels of significance.

RESULTS

Research Question One: What is the difference in the academic performance of Social Studies students taught with blended learning and lecture method in Delta State?

Table 1: Mean and standard deviation (SD) of mean performance score of Social Studies students taught with blended learning and lecture method instructional strategy

Treatment group	N	Mean	SD	Mean difference
Blended learning	62	46.61	4.07	24.36
Lecture method	65	22.25	2.54	
Total	127			

Table 1 revealed that blended learning group had a mean performance score of 46.61 with a standard deviation of 4.07, while the lecture method group had a mean performance score of 22.25 with a standard deviation of 2.54. The analysis further showed that the difference in performance between the two groups was 22.36, in favour of the students taught using the blended learning method.

Ho₂: There is no significant a significant difference in the academic performance of Social Studies students taught with blended learning and lecture method.

Table 2: ANOVA comparison of post-test performance of Social Studies students taught with blended learning instructional strategy and those taught with Lecture method

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	33891.129	2	33891.129	1164.032	.000
Within Groups	3552.065	121	29.115		
Total	37443.194	122			

Table 2 presents the ANOVA comparison of the pretest and posttest mean achievement scores of social studies students taught using blended learning strategies and lecture method. The ANOVA result indicated a statistically significant difference in the groups ($F = 1164.032$, $p < 0.05$). Consequently, the null hypothesis was rejected. This implies that there is a significant difference in the academic performance of Social Studies students taught with blended learning and lecture method.

Research Question Two: what is the difference in the mean performance score of urban and rural Social Studies students taught using blended learning instructional strategy in Delta State?

Table 3: Mean and standard deviation (SD) on the mean performance score of urban and rural Social Studies students taught using blended learning instructional strategies n Social Studies

Location	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean difference
Urban	34	48.41	.46	1.80
Rural	28	46.61	.88	
Total	62			

The analysis in table 3 revealed that difference existed in the performance of urban and rural students when taught using blended learning strategy. Urban students had a mean gain scores of 48.41 with a standard ad deviation of .46 while rural students had a performances mean score of 46.61 with standard deviation of .88. The analysis revealed that difference existed in the performance of urban and rural students when taught using blended instructional strategy, with a mean difference of 1.80 in favour of urban students.

Ho₂: There is no significant difference in the mean academic performance scores of Social Studies students taught using blended learning strategies on in Delta State.

Table 4: Mean and standard deviation (SD) on the mean performance score of urban and rural Social Studies students taught using blended learning instructional strategies n Social Studies

Location	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Df	t-cal.	p-value	Remark
Urban	34	48.41	.46				
Rural	28	46.61	.88	60	10.35	0.000	Significant
Total	62						

The analysis in Table 4 revealed that the mean performance score of urban students (M = 48.41, SD = 0.46) was higher than that of their rural counterparts (Mean = 46.61, SD = 0.88). The calculated t-value was 10.35 at 60 degrees of freedom, with a corresponding p-value of 0.000. Since the p-value was less than the 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis was rejected. This finding therefore shows that there is a statistically significant difference in the mean academic performance scores of urban and rural Social Studies students taught using blended learning instructional strategies in Delta State.

Discussion

The findings of this study revealed that there is a significant difference in the academic performance of Social Studies students taught with blended learning and those taught with the lecture method. This implies that the use of blended learning instructional strategies has a stronger positive effect on students' academic performance compared to the lecture method. The result aligns with the constructivist view of learning, which emphasizes active participation, interaction, and the integration of technology to enhance understanding. The finding also in line with Okeke, (2021) and Afolabi and Adesina, (2022) who in their various studies demonstrated the effectiveness of blended learning in improving students' comprehension, engagement, and achievement when compared with purely teacher-centered instructional methods this finding is also consistence with Alhassan and Adepoju (2021) who

revealed that blended learning combines the strengths of face-to-face instruction and digital learning resources, thereby fostering deeper understanding and retention of content. The finding also agrees with Yusuf and Afolabi (2022) who reported that students exposed to blended learning strategies tend to demonstrate higher levels of engagement and critical thinking compared to their peers who rely solely on lecture methods. The finding of this study therefore corroborates earlier reports that the integration of technology into classroom instruction increases students' motivation and enhances their academic outcomes (Igboin & Onwuachu, 2020; Ajayi, 2023). The result further aligns with the constructivist perspective, which emphasizes learner-centered approaches that encourage interaction, collaboration, and problem-solving. Lecture-based teaching often limits students to passive listening, while blended learning actively involves learners through multimedia resources, online discussions, and interactive activities. In agreement, Okechukwu and Eze (2019) highlighted that students taught through blended learning environments demonstrate superior performance due to the opportunity for self-paced study and reinforcement beyond the classroom setting. This confirms that blended learning is a viable instructional alternative for improving academic achievement in Social Studies.

The second findings indicated a statistically significant difference in the mean academic performance scores of urban and rural Social Studies students taught using blended learning instructional strategy in Delta State. This suggests that the learning environment and available resources may have influenced the extent to which students benefited from blended learning. Urban students may have had better access to digital tools, internet connectivity, and exposure to technology, thereby enhancing their ability to effectively engage in blended learning activities. On the other hand, rural students, though exposed to the same instructional strategy, might have faced challenges such as limited access to ICT resources and infrastructural deficiencies, which could have impacted their level of performance. These findings are consistent with earlier reports by Eze and Nwankwo (2020) and Adeyemi (2023), who noted that disparities in access to technological resources between urban and rural schools often create performance gaps among students when modern instructional strategies are adopted. The results therefore highlight the importance of addressing infrastructural and resource inequalities in the implementation of blended learning across school locations to ensure equity in educational outcomes. The finding is in line with Uzochukwu (2022) emphasized that disparities in access to technological tools between urban and rural areas significantly affect students' academic performance when blended learning approaches are implemented. These findings therefore suggest that while blended learning is an effective strategy, its benefits are maximized only when enabling infrastructure and resources are made equitably available to both urban and rural schools.

Conclusion

This study investigated the effect of blended learning on the academic performance of upper basic Social Studies students in Delta State. The findings revealed that students taught using blended learning strategy performed significantly better than those taught with the lecture method. This indicates that blended learning is a more effective instructional approach for enhancing students' academic performance in Social Studies. The study further established that there was a statistically significant difference in the academic performance of urban and rural students taught with blended learning. While urban students benefitted more, likely due to better access to digital resources and infrastructural facilities, rural students faced limitations that affected their performance outcomes. This underscores the need for deliberate efforts to bridge the resource and infrastructural gaps between urban and rural schools to ensure equitable learning opportunities. In conclusion, blended learning holds

great potential in transforming the teaching and learning of Social Studies at the upper basic level. However, its effectiveness depends not only on teachers' adoption of innovative pedagogical strategies but also on the provision of adequate technological support and infrastructure. If properly implemented and equitably resourced across school locations, blended learning can significantly improve academic performance and contribute to achieving quality education in Delta State.

Recommendations

The following recommendations are made based on the findings:

1. Teachers of Social Studies at the upper basic level should adopt blended learning strategy in their instructional delivery, as the method has been proven to significantly enhance students' academic performance compared to the lecture method.
2. The Ministry of Education and school administrators should organize regular training, workshops, and seminars to equip Social Studies teachers with the necessary digital literacy skills and pedagogical competencies required for effective implementation of blended learning.
3. Government should ensure the adequate provision of ICT facilities such as computers, projectors, reliable internet access, and alternative power supply in both urban and rural schools to support blended learning.
4. Special interventions should be directed toward rural schools to close the digital divide. This could include the provision of subsidized ICT devices, mobile internet solutions, and community-based ICT hubs to enable rural students to benefit equally from blended learning.

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